

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№1(2)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 726 sahifa,
20-yanvar, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

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Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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MODERN TEACHING METHODS BASED ON EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article highlights the responsibilities placed on pedagogical staff in the modern educational process and examines the issues of forming students' knowledge, skills, and abilities in accordance with modern requirements. The didactic significance of using problem-based learning, information and communication technologies, and interactive methods in the educational process—particularly the methods of “Brainstorming” and “Working in small groups”—is analyzed. The structure, advantages, and disadvantages of these methods are revealed, and their role in developing students' independent, creative, and logical thinking is substantiated.

Key words: modern education, innovative methods, problem-based learning, brainstorming, small groups, ICT, creative thinking.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida pedagog xodimlar zimmasiga yuklatilgan mas'uliyat hamda ta'lim oluvchilarning bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarini zamon talablariga mos shakllantirish masalalari yoritilgan. Ta'lim jarayonida muammoli ta'lim, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari hamda interfaol metodlardan, xususan, “Aqliy hujum” va “Kichik guruhlarda ishlash” metodlaridan foydalanishning didaktik ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Ushbu metodlarning tuzilmasi, afzallik va kamchiliklari ochib berilib, ularning ta'lim oluvchilarda mustaqil, ijodiy va mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishdagi roli asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy ta'lim, innovatsion metodlar, muammoli ta'lim, aqliy hujum, kichik guruhlar, AKT, ijodiy fikrlash.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещается ответственность, возложенная на педагогических работников в современном образовательном процессе, а также вопросы формирования знаний, умений и навыков обучающихся в соответствии с современными требованиями. Проанализирована дидактическая значимость использования в образовательном процессе проблемного обучения, информационно-коммуникационных технологий и интерактивных методов, в частности методов “Мозговой штурм” и “Работа в малых группах”. Раскрыты структура, преимущества и недостатки этих методов, обоснована их роль в развитии у обучающихся самостоятельного, творческого и логического мышления.

Ключевые слова: современное образование, инновационные методы, проблемное обучение, мозговой штурм, малые группы, ИКТ, творческое мышление.

INTRODUCTION

In order to ensure that students' knowledge, skills, and abilities meet contemporary requirements, the tasks assigned to pedagogical workers are extremely important and responsible. To fulfill these tasks, teachers—regardless of the type of educational institution in which they work—must continuously engage in self-directed professional development, improve their qualifications, and conduct scientific and creative research. Problem-based learning is grounded in the creation of various problem situations within educational activities, which are intended to activate students' independence. As a result, learners' analytical and creative abilities and skills are developed. Information and communication technologies enable unlimited enrichment of knowledge through the use of computers and the Internet.

The introduction of new methods and technologies into the education system does not imply the abolition of traditional teaching methods. Innovation constitutes an integral part of the overall educational process. For example, the “Brainstorming” method involves collecting freely expressed opinions and ideas from learners on a given problem and arriving at a specific solution based on those contributions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs the “Brainstorming” method as one of the active teaching strategies and examines its application in both oral and written forms. In the oral format, students verbally express their opinions in response to questions posed by the teacher, articulating their ideas clearly and concisely [2]. In the written format, learners record their responses briefly and accurately on paper cards, which are subsequently displayed on the board using magnets or pins, allowing the teacher to group the answers according to specific characteristics. This approach creates favorable conditions for organizing and systematizing students’ ideas. When applied correctly and constructively, the “Brainstorming” method promotes free, creative, and non-standard thinking [3], ensures the involvement of all students in the learning process, and contributes to the development of a culture of communication and discussion. Through this method, students enhance their ability to express thoughts both orally and in written form, as well as to think logically and systematically. The deliberate avoidance of evaluating expressed opinions at the initial stage encourages the emergence of diverse ideas, which in turn supports the development of creative thinking. The implementation of the “Brainstorming” method depends on the instructional goals defined by the teacher and is guided by several fundamental principles, including the non-evaluation of ideas, the acceptance of all opinions regardless of correctness, and the mandatory participation of each student [4-6]. The methodological process involves posing a problematic question, collecting and recording students’ ideas, grouping them based on shared features, and selecting the most appropriate and accurate solution. In addition, elements of the “Working in Small Groups” method are incorporated to enhance collaborative learning, whereby students are divided into small groups of 3–6 participants, provided with clear instructions, guided during task completion, and encouraged to present, discuss, and analyze their results collectively, thereby improving comprehension, communication skills, and efficient use of instructional time.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The interactive teaching methods considered above, in particular “Brainstorming” and “Working in Small Groups,” play an important role in the development of students’ (trainees’) knowledge, skills, and abilities in the modern educational process. These methods do not eliminate traditional teaching approaches; rather, they complement them, making the learning process more effective and creative. They promote students’ independent thinking, foster analytical and creative abilities, and contribute to the development of communication and cooperation skills. Through the “Brainstorming” method, students learn to think freely and non-traditionally. The main principles of this method—non-evaluation of ideas, consideration of all proposals, and active participation of each learner—help students express their opinions without fear. As a result, creative and logical thinking, as well as written and oral communication skills, are developed. Among the advantages of this method are the involvement of all students, increased interest in the topic, assessment of prior knowledge, and effective visualization of ideas.

Figure 1: Mind mapping ideas for students

Brainstorming

Set a time limit

Target a problem/goal

No judgment or criticism

Encourage all ideas

Aim for quantity

Build on ideas

Stay visual

Allow one conversation at a time

Figure 2: Brainstorming activity in the classroom

The “Working in Small Groups” method is an effective tool for developing cooperation and teamwork skills. Through group activities, learners acquire experience in interaction, distribution of responsibilities, peer learning, and respect for diverse viewpoints. The main stages of this method—group formation, task assignment, discussion, and presentation—contribute to a deeper understanding of educational content, efficient use of time, and active learner participation. As a result, students better comprehend the learning material, enhance their communication culture, and improve their ability to solve collective problems.

Overall, these interactive methods ensure an innovative approach within the education system. They help students transform from passive listeners into active participants, thereby developing analytical, creative, and social competencies. When integrated with information and communication technologies in the education system of Uzbekistan, these methods significantly improve the quality of education and contribute to the training of qualified specialists who meet modern requirements. Therefore, it is essential for teachers to continuously master these methods and apply them effectively in classroom practice. As a result, the educational process becomes not only a means of knowledge transmission but also a tool for comprehensive personal development.

CONCLUSION

In the process of education and upbringing in higher educational institutions, stimulating students' interest in learning, introducing them to modern educational technologies, and developing their professional skills make a significant contribution to the formation of a harmoniously developed personality. This, in turn, helps to overcome the ideological crisis of modern society.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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2026. №1(2)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.